

IMPROVING REHABILITATION OUTCOMES AFTER ARTHROSCOPIC MENISCECTOMY THROUGH THE USE OF PHYSIOTHERAPEUTIC PROCEDURES.

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ABSTRACT

This study is based on the analysis of postoperative outcomes and rehabilitation in 60 patients who underwent surgery for meniscal pathology of the knee joints. Follow-up was conducted over a period of 1.5 to 6 months after surgery from 2023 to 2024 at the 2nd Clinic of the National Center for Rehabilitation and Prosthetics for Persons with Disabilities. The study presents the results of a comprehensive assessment, including clinical (orthopedic and neurological), radiological, MRI, and physiological examinations.

Relevance:

Meniscal injuries are among the most common intra-articular injuries of the knee joint and lead to disruption of its normal function [1–3]. According to Azizov M.Zh, the medial meniscus is damaged in 80–90% of cases, whereas the lateral meniscus is affected in 10–20%. This distribution is related to the anatomical features of the medial meniscus. In recent years, ultrasound (US), MRI, and diagnostic arthroscopy of the knee joint have been widely used for diagnosis [4,5].

One of the key advantages of MRI is its ability to detect even minimal soft tissue damage, making it an indispensable tool for diagnosing conditions such as osteoarthritis, meniscal tears, inflammatory diseases, as well as ligament and cartilage injuries. MRI allows precise localization of injuries, assessment of their severity, and planning of appropriate treatment. However, despite its advantages, MRI has limitations—particularly in cases of knee joint synovitis. The accuracy of MRI diagnosis can depend on various factors: equipment quality, specialist expertise, and patient-specific conditions (e.g., the presence of metal implants can distort results). According to several studies, MRI accuracy in diagnosing knee joint injuries ranges from 70% to 90%, indicating existing limitations in its use [7,8].

In recent years, arthroscopy and arthroscopic treatment have gained significant importance in orthopedics [1,6]. Like in other medical fields, modern technologies are actively developing in orthopedics. Despite significant progress, unsatisfactory outcomes persist in the postoperative period. As with other surgeries, complications after arthroscopic meniscectomy may occur, negatively affecting patients' quality of life.

Many researchers note that the primary cause of complications is incomplete diagnosis considering concomitant diseases, as well as delayed rehabilitation.

Given the above issues, this study is timely and relevant.

Objective:

To improve rehabilitation outcomes after arthroscopic meniscectomy using physiotherapeutic procedures.

Materials and Methods:

In 2024, arthroscopic meniscectomy was performed on 60 patients at the 2nd Clinic of the National Center for Rehabilitation and Prosthetics for Persons with Disabilities. Patient ages ranged from 25 to 60 years; 48 were men and 12 women, with a mean age of 35. The distribution by meniscal injury type was as follows: 49 patients with medial meniscus tears (group 1), 9 patients with lateral meniscus tears (group 2), and 2 patients with tears of both menisci (group 3).

To assess early rehabilitation outcomes after arthroscopic meniscectomy, patients were divided into two groups. The control group included 30 patients who received no postoperative rehabilitation such as therapeutic exercise (TE) or physiotherapy. The main group included 30 patients who received a complex of physiotherapeutic procedures, including magnetotherapy, ultrahigh-frequency therapy (UHF), shockwave therapy, and electrical stimulation.

All patients underwent clinical and laboratory evaluations, including complete blood count, C-reactive protein (CRP) level, coagulation profile, MRI of the knee joint, and basometry using goniometry to assess range of motion and functional impairment. CRP level was used to evaluate inflammation, as it is a marker of inflammatory processes. Coagulation tests assessed hemostasis and thrombotic risk, important in the postoperative period. MRI provided detailed visualization of knee joint anatomy, including menisci, ligaments, and cartilage, and detected tissue damage. Basometry with goniometry measured angular joint motion limitations precisely. Pain syndrome in the knee was also assessed to evaluate pain intensity, its dynamics, and correlation with other clinical parameters.

Results and Discussion:

All 60 patients underwent surgery after thorough evaluation of complaints, history, clinical examination, and diagnostic findings. Clinical examination revealed meniscal pain and positive signs of meniscal tears (Baikov, Voskresensky, Khitrov, Perelman signs). Active and passive knee movements caused pain, worsening with flexion. Patients exhibited limping on the operated leg, indicating functional load disturbance and restricted joint range of motion. Pronounced swelling indicated inflammation requiring monitoring and treatment.

Standard arthroscopy under spinal anesthesia was performed. In the main group, 25 had medial meniscus injuries, 4 had lateral meniscus tears, and 1 had both menisci injured. In the control group, 24 had medial meniscus injuries, 5 lateral, and 1 had both menisci injured. Partial meniscectomy and knee joint lavage were performed.

The postoperative period included a two-day hospital stay followed by recommended self-directed therapeutic exercise at home, adjusted for pain and swelling severity.

Control group patients did not receive physiotherapy or perform prescribed therapeutic exercises. Main group patients began physiotherapy on postoperative day 10 and underwent daily therapeutic exercise in outpatient settings for 10 days at a specialized rehabilitation center.

This protocol allowed assessment of the impact of early physiotherapy and systematic exercise on postoperative recovery dynamics.

Physiotherapeutic Procedures Used:

1. **Magnetotherapy** – improves microcirculation and reduces inflammation. Application: Low-frequency magnetotherapy (30–100 Hz) applied to the operated limb for 10 minutes daily over 10 days.

2. **Ultrahigh-Frequency Therapy (UHF)** – reduces swelling, inflammation, and pain. Frequencies: 40.68 MHz to 27.12 MHz provide deep tissue warming, improving microcirculation and accelerating tissue recovery. Initially performed every other day or 2–3 times per week, then daily for 10–15 minutes over 10 days.

3. **Shockwave Therapy (SWT)** – prevents muscle hypotrophy and accelerates muscle strength recovery. Five sessions every two days targeting muscles such as quadriceps, iliopsoas, and biceps femoris for treatment of injuries and inflammation.

4. **Electrical Stimulation** – 20 minutes daily for 10 days. Devices such as “Amicron” and “Diadens” were used, offering various modes and intensities for effective tissue and muscle recovery.

Dynamic Study:

In the control group, patients were evaluated every 15 days postoperatively for joint range of motion, swelling, pain, muscle tone, and limping. These parameters were compared with the main group.

In the first 15 days post-op, 18 control patients had swelling, limited motion (especially flexion $\leq 90^\circ$), pain (VAS score 6), and muscle pain rated 4. Most exhibited limping, varying from mild to moderate, indicating partial joint dysfunction and insufficient recovery.

At 30 days, 5 control patients still showed swelling, movement limitations, pain (VAS 4–5), and moderate limping, suggesting slow recovery and need for physiotherapy.

At 45 days, 3 control patients continued to exhibit swelling, movement restriction, pain, and limping. For these, comprehensive physiotherapy was recommended to improve range of motion, reduce swelling and pain, restore normal muscle tone, and correct limping.

Control group clinical progression showed gradual symptom reduction, but full functional recovery required additional rehabilitation including physiotherapy.

Main Group Clinical Results:

Within 15 days post-op, 5 patients showed limping, moderate swelling, flexion limited to 90° , and mild pain (VAS 3). Muscle pain was rated at 4. By 30 days, complaints persisted in only 1 patient, indicating significant improvement. At 45 days, clinical symptoms including swelling, movement limitation, pain, and muscle soreness disappeared completely in all main group patients.

These results confirm faster and more pronounced functional recovery in the main group, likely due to effective rehabilitation involving physiotherapy and therapeutic exercise.

Comparative outcomes 15 days post-operation

Symptom	Main Group (n=30)	Control Group (n=30)
Flexion limited to 90°	5 patients	18 patients
Swelling	5 patients	18 patients

Pain (VAS score)	5 (VAS 3)	18 (VAS 6)
Muscle tone (score)	5 (4 points)	18 (4 points)
Limping	5 patients	18 patients

Comparative outcomes 30 days post-operation

Symptom	Main Group (n=30)	Control Group (n=30)
Flexion limited to 90°	1 patient	5 patients
Swelling	1 patient	5 patients
Pain (VAS score)	1 (VAS 0 — no pain)	5 (VAS 4–5)
Muscle tone (score)	1 (0 points)	5 (4–5 points)
Limping	1 patient	5 patients

Comparative outcomes 45 days post-operation

Symptom	Main Group (n=30)	Control Group (n=30)
Flexion limited to 90°	0 patients	3 patients
Swelling	0 patients	3 patients
Pain (VAS score)	0 (VAS 0 – no pain)	3 (VAS 0 – no pain)
Muscle tone (score)	0 patients	3 patients
Limping	0 patients	3 patients

Case example and study results

Patient O., born in 1969, diagnosed with a post-traumatic chronic tear of the posterior horn of the medial meniscus of the left knee joint accompanied by pain syndrome. The results of the study confirm the high effectiveness of physiotherapeutic procedures in the rehabilitation process after arthroscopic meniscectomy, which significantly accelerated pain reduction and improved functional status of the knee joint. Specifically, the use of physiotherapeutic methods expedited the restoration of range of motion and reduced swelling, which in turn positively influenced the normalization of joint activity. Analysis of patient progress dynamics demonstrated that a complex of physiotherapeutic interventions promotes faster normalization of functions such as movement, muscle tone, and pain reduction, confirming the effectiveness of the chosen methods. Our data are consistent with the findings of Rotini M. [9], who also established that early application of physiotherapy after meniscectomy significantly accelerates recovery, reduces time to full functional restoration, and minimizes pain manifestations. This underscores the importance of physiotherapeutic intervention as an integral part of postoperative treatment, facilitating knee joint recovery. Nevertheless, despite considerable functional improvements within the first months post-operation, some patients did not achieve full functional recovery three months after completion of the rehabilitation course. Residual symptoms, including limping, persisted in some cases. Limping, despite improvement in joint condition, remained in a small number of patients, which is associated with incomplete restoration of range of motion and mild pain at the surgical site. This factor likely indicates the need for prolonged rehabilitation or the introduction of additional corrective methods for residual joint dysfunction. Thus, the study results show that despite marked improvements in the early postoperative period, full restoration of knee joint function and elimination of symptoms such as limping may require a

longer rehabilitation period and additional physiotherapeutic procedures aimed at enhancing functional parameters and reducing residual effects.

Conclusion:

1. The use of physiotherapeutic methods after arthroscopic meniscectomy significantly reduces pain syndrome, improves joint mobility, and accelerates recovery of static and dynamic function of the operated joint.

2. The most effective methods are magnetotherapy, shockwave therapy, and electrical stimulation.

3. Early physiotherapy after arthroscopic meniscectomy allowed reduction of patients' temporary disability period by 1.5 months, ensuring economic benefits of the surgery and rehabilitation process.

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